

Deep Learning-Based Image Similarity Assessment Using ONNX Runtime

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Abstract— It explores the integration of deep learning techniques, specifically Siamese networks, with web applications to enable accessible image similarity analysis. The deep learning model, implemented using the ONNX framework, is used to extract essential image features and compute image similarities using cosine distance metrics. The seminar aims to demystify the model's inner workings and present a Flask-based web application for image similarity assessments. The seminar reviews literature on image similarity analysis, deep learning techniques, and Siamese networks, and discusses experiments and results. The seminar highlights the transformative potential of image similarity analysis in various applications and paves the way for future research.

Keywords—ONNX framework, Convolutional Neural Networks, Image Similarity Assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

Image similarity assessment is a crucial task in computer vision and image analysis, with applications in fields like content-based image retrieval, plagiarism detection, and medical image analysis. Deep learning techniques, particularly Siamese networks, have revolutionized this process. This seminar explores the integration of these techniques and their real-world deployment via a Flask-based web application. The seminar focuses on the ONNX framework, a pre-trained architecture for feature extraction and similarity scoring, and the development and deployment of a Flask-based web application. The seminar covers the inner workings of the deep learning model, its cosine distance metrics, and the development and deployment of a Flask-based web application. The seminar aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of image similarity analysis using deep learning and showcase its practical implementation via a web application, making the technology accessible and usable for a broader audience.

II. ONNX RUNTIME FRAMEWORK

Microsoft co-developed ONNX, an open standard for traditional machine learning models and deep learning, with Facebook and AWS. The ONNX format serves as the cornerstone of an open ecosystem that increases the value and accessibility of AI for all parties involved: hardware vendors may simplify neural network computing optimizations,

developers can select the best framework for the job at hand, and framework authors can concentrate on creative upgrades. To make it quick and easy to operationalize models, teams were employing a variety of training frameworks and aiming for different deployment options, thus it was imperative to bring these disparate solutions together. That solution is offered by ONNX Runtime. It provides data scientists with the freedom to develop, refine, and produce models with excellent performance inside the framework of their choice. An open-source project called ONNX Runtime aims to speed up machine learning on a variety of hardware platforms, operating systems, and frameworks. With just one set of APIs, it allows for the acceleration of machine learning inferencing across all your deployment targets. To find optimization opportunities and give you access to the best hardware acceleration available, ONNX Runtime automatically parses through your model. Additionally, ONNX Runtime provides training acceleration, a feature that has been demonstrated in production workloads such as Office 365, Bing, and Visual Studio and incorporates innovations from Microsoft Research.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Image similarity analysis is a crucial task that measures the similarity between images based on their visual content. Traditional methods often struggle with image complexity and variability. [1] It discusses traditional methods and their limitations, particularly in dealing with complex data. It introduces Siamese networks, their role in deep learning, and their applications in image similarity tasks. It also discusses the impact of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in image analysis, transfer learning, pre-trained models, web-based interfaces, experimental approaches, innovations, bridging the gap, empowering users, and the transformative potential of advanced image similarity analysis in various industries. It calls for future research in the field of image similarity analysis using deep learning and web-based interfaces. [2] It introduces the concept of image similarity assessment and its applications in image retrieval, object recognition, and matching. It discusses traditional methods for measuring image similarity, such as pixel-by-pixel comparison, and introduces feature-based methods like ORB

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(Oriented Fast Rotated Brief). The text also discusses the Brute Force Matcher and compares ORB with other feature detectors. The text also discusses the applications of ORB in image similarity assessments, its challenges and limitations, and potential future enhancements. The text concludes by emphasizing the importance of efficient and accurate image similarity assessments in various fields. [3] It discusses traditional IQA metrics like Mean Squared Error, Structural Similarity Index, and Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio, which may not fully capture the perceptual quality of images as perceived by the Human Visual System (HVS). The FSIM Index, a low-level feature-based IQA metric, is introduced, based on the idea that HVS perceives images primarily through its salient low-level features. The FSIM Index is further extended by incorporating image chromatic features, enhancing its ability to assess image quality comprehensively. Comparative analysis is presented, with promising results and robustness.

IV. MOTIVATION

"Image Similarity Analysis using Deep Learning and Web Application Integration" aims to address the critical need of quantifying image similarity in the digital world. The seminar focuses on enhancing user experience by creating an accessible web interface for image comparison. The seminar is grounded in real-world relevance, with applications in various industries such as e-commerce and healthcare. It aims to bridge the gap between advanced research in deep learning and its practical application, making the technology accessible to a broader audience. The seminar also focuses on empowering users, ensuring they can use the technology for their specific needs. The seminar also encourages innovation and future exploration in the field of image similarity analysis.

V. DATA AND EXPERIMENTATION

The image similarity analysis process involves a diverse dataset of images, including pairs of images with known similarity labels. Data preprocessing is crucial to ensure uniformity and compatibility with the deep learning model. Similarity scoring is performed using the cosine similarity metric. A Flask-based web application is developed to provide a user-friendly interface for image similarity analysis. Experiments are conducted to evaluate the accuracy and performance of the deep learning model and the web application. Validation is performed by comparing the model's predictions with ground-truth labels from the dataset. The results are discussed, emphasizing the strengths and limitations of the proposed methodology. Future exploration may involve exploring different deep learning architectures, enhancing the web application, or extending the methodology to handle larger datasets or real-time image analysis.

VI. PROPOSED METHDOLOGY

This study focuses on the development of a deep learning model for image similarity analysis. The model uses a diverse dataset of images, with known similarity labels, and is pre-trained using models like VGG, ResNet, or Inception. The model is then fine-tuned using image pairs with known similarity labels. The model extracts feature from the input images, which are then used for similarity scoring. The model is then integrated into a Flask web application, which displays the results based on the similarity threshold. . Experiments are conducted to evaluate the model's accuracy and performance. The results are then validated by comparing the model's predictions with ground-truth labels from the dataset. The study concludes by discussing the strengths and limitations of the proposed methodology and discussing the practical implications of the technology for real-world scenarios. Future work includes exploring different deep learning architectures, enhancing the web application, or extending the methodology to handle larger datasets or real-time image analysis.

A. MODEL SELECTION

The text outlines the process of selecting an appropriate model for image similarity checking. It begins by defining the problem and explaining the model's relevance. The model's architecture is detailed, including layers and unique features. Pre-training and transfer learning are discussed, along with its evaluation and performance. The model's architecture is suitable for feature extraction, and its computational efficiency is assessed. The model's selection considerations include accuracy vs. computational cost, fine-tuning, and robustness against image variations. Alternatives and comparisons are mentioned, and future model choices or improvements are discussed. References to relevant research papers are provided to support the chosen model.

B. FEATURE EXTRACTION

It discusses the types of features extracted, such as deep learning features, and their role in capturing essential information. The text also discusses the pre-processing steps used, such as resizing, normalization, and color space conversions, as well as dimensionality reduction techniques like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or t-SNE. The feature vector size, normalization, and scaling techniques are also discussed. The text also discusses the specific deep learning model used for feature extraction, the training data used, fine-tuning and adaptation, and the time required for feature extraction. It also discusses the model's ability to maintain feature stability and invariance, and its interpretability and transferability. The text concludes with comparisons with handcrafted features and references to relevant research papers.

VII. RESULTS

Accuracy evaluation is a method used to measure the effectiveness of a system in detecting image similarity. It involves evaluating performance metrics such as accuracy,

precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC. The dataset used for evaluation is described, including its size, splitting, ground truth, evaluation process, threshold selection, and results presentation. A confusion matrix is provided to illustrate true positives, false positives, false negatives, and false negatives. The ROC curve is used to visualize the trade-off between true positive and false positive rates. Results are interpreted and compared with baseline models or existing methods. The system's robustness is discussed, and any limitations or challenges are addressed. Future work is suggested to improve accuracy and address identified limitations. The conclusion summarizes key findings and its relevance to the overall success of the system.

Image Similarity Check

Select Anchor Image: frame.jpg

Select Probe Image: frame1.jpg

Results:

Image Similarity Result

The model thinks the images aren't the same

Accuracy: 58.040373872744496%

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VIII. CONCLUSION

The FSIM (Feature Similarity Index) is a low-level feature-based Image Quality Assessment (IQA) metric that uses Phase Congruency (PC) and Gradient Magnitude (GM) to assess image quality from the Human Visual System (HVS). The metric has been extended to account for chromatic features, enhancing its ability to evaluate image quality. Extensive comparative analysis against eight prominent IQA metrics showed that FSIM and its extension consistently outperformed other metrics, particularly when evaluating images with various distortion types. The system's robustness and accuracy make it suitable for practical applications like content-based image retrieval and quality control in image databases. Future research could explore additional feature types and real-world applications benefiting from accurate image quality assessment.

IX. REFERENCES

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